

TA_DA: Target-Aware Data Anonymization

SERGIO BAREZZANI (Senior Member, IEEE),

SABRINA DE CAPITANI DI VIMERCATI (Senior Member, IEEE),
VALERIO GHIRIMOLDI (Fellow, IEEE)

Università degli Studi di Milano, 20133 Milan, Italy

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: PIERANGELA SAMARATI (email: pierangela.samarati@unimi.it).

This work was supported in part by the EC under projects Chips JU EdgeAI (101097300) and GLACIATION (101070141), by the Italian MUR under PRIN project POLAR (2022LA8XBH), and by project SERICS (PE00000014) under the MUR NRRP funded by the EU - NGEU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Italian MUR. Neither the European Union nor the Italian MUR can be held responsible for them.

ABSTRACT More and more scenarios rely today on data analysis of massive amount of data, possibly contributed from multiple parties (data controllers). Data may, however, contain information that is sensitive, company-confidential, or that should be protected (e.g., since it exposes identities of the data subjects) and cannot simply be freely shared and used for analysis. Business rules, restrictions from individuals (data subjects to which data refer), as well as privacy regulations demand data to be sanitized before being released or shared with others. Unfortunately, such protection typically comes with a loss of utility of the released data, for analytics tasks operating on the data. In this paper, we present TA_DA, a target-aware data anonymization approach that aims at protecting (anonymizing) data while preserving as much as possible the utility of the released data for the data analytics task operating downstream. Our approach does not replace anonymization solutions, it operates prior to anonymization catering data for the anonymization process. The idea is to partition data in groups (constructed based on the data analytics task to which the data are fed) on which anonymization then operates. With anonymization achieved through data generalization (to provide k -anonymity and ℓ -diversity guarantees), the goal of having anonymization operate independently on groups is to limit the impact of anonymization on the attributes and values that should be preserved for the downstream data analytics task. Our experimental evaluation confirms the effectiveness of our approach.

INDEX TERMS Target-aware data anonymization, clustering, machine learning classifier.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's society is highly dependent on data, with huge (and ever increasing) amount of data generated, collected, and processed. Concepts such as Big Data, data analytics, and machine learning are today common terms for the layperson, witnessing their pervasiveness in every context of our daily life. As a matter of fact, the availability of massive amount of data, together with powerful and efficient computational infrastructures and services, and hence the ability to extract knowledge from data, is at the heart of our smart society, bringing great benefits in diverse domains, from business to leisure.

More and more scenarios rely today on different parties contributing to the collection, sharing, and analysis of data. However, often original datasets include information that cannot be freely shared. This is, for example, the case of data

referred to individuals, whose privacy needs to be protected, as demanded by data regulations (e.g., [1], [2]). Indeed, the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the California Consumer Protection Act (CCPA), and other similar regulations worldwide, demand protection for information referred to individuals (data subjects) whose identity and sensitive information should be properly protected through data anonymization solutions (with anonymized data being exempt from the obligations set out in the regulations).

Notwithstanding the great benefit of operating on data, it is therefore of utmost importance to ensure that the privacy of data subjects (i.e., entities or individuals to which the data refer) be properly protected in such data sharing and analytics process. When data analysis is performed by external parties (other than the data controller responsible for the data), this

FIGURE 1. Reference scenario.

implies that data should be properly anonymized before being released. Unfortunately, anonymization, which by design causes information loss (for a privacy gain), can have a significant negative impact on the performance of the downstream data analytics task, with the known tension between privacy and utility.

In this paper, we consider a scenario characterized by multiple parties (data controllers) contributing data for a data analytics task. We consider classification and clustering as data analytics tasks, and present a technique that both protects the privacy of data subjects and maintains the utility of the anonymized data with respect to the task to which data are fed. Fig. 1 shows our reference scenario, with data controllers anonymizing their data before releasing them for the global knowledge base on which the data analytics task operates. Our data anonymization approach, called TA_DA (Target-Aware Data Anonymization), anonymizes data aware of the data analytics task to which data are contributed, with the goal of minimizing the effect of protection on the data analysis to be executed. A preliminary version of this work, considering the task of data classification, appeared in [3]. In this paper, we extend our earlier proposal by also considering clustering as downstream analytics task.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II illustrates the basic concepts. Section III describes the problem addressed and the rationale of our approach. Sections IV and V describe the two steps of TA_DA: target-aware partitioning and group anonymization, respectively. Section VI illustrates the results of our experimental evaluation. Section VII presents some considerations and aspects open to further investigation. Section VIII discusses related work. Finally, Section IX presents our conclusions. Appendixes A and B available as supplementary material, report a theorem on the approach and the TA_DA pseudocode, respectively.

II. BASIC CONCEPTS

We consider anonymization of datasets to be contributed to a data analytics task. Wishing to operate with truthful information for data analytics, we assume anonymization to be carried out according to k -anonymity [4] enhanced with

	Age	State	Job	Income		Age	State	Job	Income		Age	State	Job	Income
t_1	51	MN	Gov	150	t_2	[30-35]	CA	Non-gov	150	t_1	[37-62]	MN	Gov	150
t_2	30	CA	Non-gov	150	t_3	[30-35]	CA	Non-gov	120	t_5	[37-62]	MN	Gov	200
t_3	35	CA	Non-gov	120	t_7	[62-64]	CA	Gov	300	t_8	[37-62]	MN	Non-gov	150
t_4	18	TX	Gov	300	t_{11}	[62-64]	CA	Gov	250	t_2	[24-35]	[CA,MN]	Non-gov	150
t_5	62	MN	Gov	200	t_1	[51-62]	MN	Gov	150	t_3	[24-35]	[CA,MN]	Non-gov	120
t_6	40	TX	Gov	300	t_5	[51-62]	MN	Gov	200	t_{10}	[24-35]	[CA,MN]	Gov	100
t_7	62	CA	Gov	300	t_8	[24-37]	MN	Non-gov	150	t_4	[18-36]	TX	Gov	300
t_8	37	MN	Non-gov	150	t_{10}	[24-37]	MN	Gov	100	t_9	[18-36]	TX	Gov	180
t_9	36	TX	Gov	180	t_4	[18-40]	TX	Gov	300	t_{12}	[18-36]	TX	Gov	300
t_{10}	24	MN	Gov	100	t_6	[18-40]	TX	Gov	300	t_6	[40-64]	[CA,TX]	Gov	300
t_{11}	64	CA	Gov	250	t_9	[18-40]	TX	Gov	180	t_7	[40-64]	[CA,TX]	Gov	300
t_{12}	20	TX	Gov	300	t_{12}	[18-40]	TX	Gov	300	t_{11}	[40-64]	[CA,TX]	Gov	250

FIGURE 2. An example of original relation (a) and of two (2,2)-anonymous versions of the original relation (b)–(c).

ℓ -diversity [5]. We assume datasets to be anonymized to be relational tables, where each relation R is characterized by a set $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ of attributes comprising:

- *identifiers*: attributes identifying data subjects, that is, entities to which data refer (we consider these attributes to be removed before release and therefore discard them from our treatment);
- *quasi-identifier*: set of attributes that jointly can, through linking with other sources, possibly reduce the uncertainty about identities of data subjects;
- *sensitive*: attribute whose values, in association with (the identity of) data subjects, are considered sensitive and should therefore be protected.

Data anonymization through k -anonymity and ℓ -diversity implies generalizing values of the quasi-identifier attributes to ensure each combination of (generalized) values of quasi-identifier attributes appearing in the table to occur at least k times (k -anonymity), and each group of tuples with the same generalized quasi-identifying values to have at least ℓ well-represented sensitive values (ℓ -diversity). We consider generalization applied at the level of cell (in contrast to the whole attribute column), hence operating at finest possible grain to limit information loss [6]. We represent the generalized value for a set of values as the interval between the minimum and maximum values in the set for continuous (i.e., numerical) attributes, and as the set comprising all the values for categorical attributes. Also, for simplicity, we assume the well-represented criterion of ℓ -diversity to be enforced by requiring each group to include at least ℓ different values. The case $\ell = 1$ implies requiring only k -anonymity to hold with no restriction on the occurrences of the sensitive values. We refer to a transformed (generalized) version of a relation satisfying k -anonymity and ℓ -diversity as a (k, ℓ) -anonymous version of the relation. Fig. 2 illustrates an example of original relation and two possible (2,2)-anonymous versions of it, considering Age and State to work as quasi-identifier and attribute Income to be sensitive.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION AND SKETCH OF THE APPROACH

Our reference scenario is characterized by multiple *data controllers* contributing data for a data analytics task operating on the collective information from the different controllers. As data analytics task, we consider *classification* and

clustering as representative of a supervised and of an unsupervised learning approach, respectively.

Classification is a machine learning method that predicts the class of input data. It is based on a training phase that uses *labeled data* for learning a model (classifier) able to predict the class (i.e., the value of a class label attribute) associated with unseen data. Intuitively, classification learns dependencies of a given attribute (*label*) from other attributes (*predictors*) in the dataset. Datasets contributed by data controllers collectively represent the training data from which the classification task learns. We therefore consider a dataset $R(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ to be released by a data controller contributing to the data analytics task to include, besides the quasi-identifier and sensitive attributes, also a *label* attribute, denoted λ , of interest for the classification task for which data are released. Note that the label attribute cannot coincide with the sensitive attribute as we aim at maintaining as much as possible the correct prediction of the label attribute while protecting instead inferences on the sensitive attribute.

Clustering is a machine learning method that partitions the input dataset in clusters to maximize *similarity* among tuples in the same cluster and *dissimilarity* of tuples in different clusters. Similarity between tuples can be measured in different ways (e.g., using a distance metric), also depending on the kind of data (i.e., numeric vs categorical). Datasets contributed by data controllers collectively represent the data on which the clustering task operates.

Data used for classification or clustering may contain identifying, quasi-identifying, or sensitive information, and therefore should be anonymized before being released to external parties. As said, we assume anonymization with k -anonymity and ℓ -diversity, and hence the release to the data analytics task of (k, ℓ) -anonymous datasets. Anonymization is enforced independently by each data controller, which could even operate with different values of k and ℓ , depending on the degree of protection wished.

The problem then becomes the possible negative impact of anonymization on the ability of the data analytics task to perform classification/clustering. For instance, in the case of a classification task if attributes that represent good predictors of the label are generalized in the anonymization, the classification will be operating with less information (suffering the information loss caused by generalization). Analogously, in case of a clustering task, generalization modifies the distance among tuples, potentially affecting the quality of clustering. Since different anonymous versions of a table can exist, corresponding to different groups of generalized tuples and/or generalization of different attributes/values in the quasi-identifier, our goal is the definition of an anonymization process aware of the data analytics task to be executed downstream and driven by it.

Basically, the problem we address can be formulated as follows: *Given a relational table $R(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ where the set $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ of attributes includes quasi-identifier attributes QI , a sensitive attribute s , and possibly a label attribute λ , compute a (k, ℓ) -anonymous version of R that performs well*

FIGURE 3. Overall working of our target-aware data anonymization.

for a machine learning task (i.e., classification with target λ or clustering).

In other words, we aim for an anonymization that preserves as much as possible the characteristics of the dataset that the downstream classification/clustering task leverages. This implies, for classification tasks, to aim for a generalized version of the dataset that maintains as specific as possible the values of the predictor attributes in the quasi-identifier on which the label values depend more, generalizing instead values of other attributes on which the label attribute is less (or no) dependent. For a clustering task, this instead implies to aim for a generalized version of the dataset that preserves as much as possible the similarity among the tuples that would belong (with respect to original data) to the same cluster and the dissimilarity among tuples that would belong (with respect to original data) to different clusters. We achieve these goals by applying the anonymization process on subsets of the dataset, where each subset groups tuples that are similar (e.g., tuples that are equal or most similar with respect to predictor attribute values or that belong to the same cluster), so that generalization has a limited impact on the result of the downstream analytics task.

Our approach, called **TA_DA**, comprises two steps (Fig. 3):

- *target-aware partitioning* operates on the original datasets by partitioning tuples in groups. For classification, the partition of the dataset is driven by the label of the classification task. More precisely, groups are defined through a decision tree, built over quasi-identifier attributes only, and guided by the classification label. For clustering, the partition of the dataset is computed using a clustering algorithm that considers all the attributes of the dataset, with the exclusion of the sensitive attribute (which clearly needs to be protected against inferences).
- *group anonymization* applied to each group of tuples produced in the previous step (leaf nodes in the decision tree and clusters, respectively) with a classical anonymization approach.

Since the target-aware data anonymization is enforced independently by each data controller before releasing data, in the following we illustrate our approach with reference to a single dataset. We will consider the presence of multiple of such anonymized datasets used for the same data analytics task in the experimental evaluation (see Section VI).

Example III.1 (Running example): As running example, we consider the table in Fig. 2(a), where the pair $\langle \text{Age}, \text{State} \rangle$ is the quasi-identifier, Income is the sensitive attribute, and Job is the label for the classification task to which data are

to be contributed (the example omits identifiers and other attributes since they are not relevant for illustrating the work). We will also refer to the two (2,2)-anonymous versions of the table reported in Fig. 2(b)–(c).

IV. TARGET-AWARE PARTITIONING

We describe in more details the first phase of TA_DA. Section IV-A and Section IV-B describe how data are partitioned assuming classification and clustering, respectively, as downstream data analytics task.

A. CLASSIFICATION

For classification, partitioning of tuples aims at producing groups of tuples that - when generalized - best preserve the correlation between (generalized) quasi-identifier and label values. Intuitively, this corresponds to maintaining in the same group tuples with the same (or as close as possible) values for predictor attributes in the quasi-identifier, so that generalization will have limited or no impact on them. Of course, predictors are not known, but should be learned from the data themselves.

Our approach to such target-aware partitioning is to use a machine learning algorithm based on a *decision tree* to make predictions. In other words, we create a model that predicts the value of the label attribute by learning *decision rules* from the values of the other (quasi-identifier) attributes.

The construction of a decision tree starts from the root node that represents the whole dataset. The decision tree is then recursively built by splitting the dataset represented by a node into subsets that are represented as its child nodes. More precisely, for each node in the tree, a set of possible split values is identified for each attribute. The algorithm for the construction of the decision tree selects the attribute and the split value(s) that are most significant with respect to a specific criterion defined on the label [7] (e.g., maximization of information gain). This process terminates when a stopping condition is satisfied (e.g., the values of the label attribute for the tuples in the leaf nodes are sufficiently uniform or all the attributes have been used for splitting). By construction, the attributes used in the splitting operations are those on which the label attribute depends more since they permit to partition the tuples in groups that are more similar with respect to the label attribute. Furthermore, the tuples in these groups are also similar with respect to the attributes considered by splitting operations, since they all satisfy the same decision rules (i.e., the if-then rules defined over the attributes used in the splitting operation).

We adapt this classical construction of a decision tree to our goal. First, we only use the quasi-identifier attributes for the splitting operations. Other attributes, including the sensitive attribute, are not considered. The rationale for using the quasi-identifier attributes only is that, as previously mentioned, the construction of the decision tree identifies the (quasi-identifier) attributes on which the label depends more and tuples with similar values for these attributes are grouped together, which is exactly what we need. The reason

FIGURE 4. An example of decision tree built over the relation in Fig. 2(a).

for not using the sensitive attribute (e.g., Income for our running example) is the need to ensure diversity of its values in each generalized group. The reason for not considering other attributes is that they are not affected by generalization and their values therefore are never impacted by the process. Using them not only would not help but could actually have negative effect, as it might prevent optimal consideration of quasi-identifier predictors in the partitioning (which would eventually result in more generalization on them). Second, we add the condition that a node can be split only if the resulting child nodes represent a partition of the parent relation with a sufficient number of tuples for satisfying the k -anonymity and ℓ -diversity requirements. Intuitively, this requires (as a necessary, but not sufficient, condition) the parent node to have at least $2k$ tuples to permit at least a binary split such that the two child nodes have k tuples each. Also, we perform a split only if each child node would have at least ℓ well-represented values for the sensitive attribute. Each leaf node of a decision tree built considering these two changes is therefore a node that, by construction, represents a group of tuples of size at least k and with at least ℓ well-represented values for the sensitive attribute. This target-aware partitioning phase produces a (k, ℓ) -compliant decision tree, formally defined as follows.

Definition IV.1 ((k, ℓ)-compliant decision tree): Let $R(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ be a relation with QI , s , and λ the quasi-identifier, sensitive, and label attributes in $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$, respectively, and $DT(N, E)$ be a decision tree built over R for predicting label attribute λ , with N the set of nodes and E the set of edges. DT is a (k, ℓ) -compliant decision tree iff for each leaf node $n \in N$, the set of tuples R_n represented by n is such that $|R_n| \geq k$ and R_n includes tuples with at least ℓ well-represented values for s .

Example IV.1 (Decision tree): Fig. 4 illustrates an example of a decision tree built over the relation in Fig. 2(a). The root node coincides with the whole table that is split over attribute State. The resulting children correspond to the set of tuples of employees working in California (CA), Minnesota (MN), and Texas (TX). For employees working in California, there is a further split that distinguishes between employees with

age less than or equal to 40 and over 40. The leaf nodes are labeled with either ‘Gov’ or ‘Non-gov’ as job. For each node, attributes with a light blue (gray in b/w printout) background are those used for splitting, and attributes with gray values are the attributes that cannot be used for splitting (i.e., sensitive attribute or attributes already used for split). In this tree, for example, the leftmost leaf node corresponding to the set $\{t_2, t_3\}$ of tuples is associated with a decision rule of the form “IF State=CA AND Age \leq 40 THEN Job is ‘Non-gov’”. The decision tree is (2,2)-compliant since each leaf node represents a group of at least two tuples with at least two different values for the sensitive attribute Income.

B. CLUSTERING

For clustering, the partitioning of tuples aims at preserving as much as possible the hidden patterns in the data. To this purpose, TA_DA partitions the dataset through a clustering algorithm [8], which aims at maximizing *similarity* (e.g., minimum distance) among tuples in the same cluster and the *dissimilarity* (i.e., diversity) between tuples in different clusters. Intuitively, being the tuples in the same cluster similar also according to the quasi-identifier attributes, generalization for achieving anonymity will have a limited effect on the tuples in the cluster, thus preserving as much as possible their similarity (and dissimilarity w.r.t. those in other clusters) and the hidden patterns in the data.

Clustering algorithms leverage a representation of the data as points in a multi-dimensional space, mapping each attribute to a dimension and each data item to a point in such space. Classical clustering algorithms need to be adapted to our goal. First, we do not consider sensitive attributes in clustering since, like for classification, we need to ensure diversity of the values of the sensitive attribute among the tuples in each cluster (ℓ -diversity). Note instead that, differently from classification, for clustering we consider also attributes that do not belong to the quasi-identifier, because clustering aims to identify hidden patterns in the data, which can depend on any attribute. Second, the similarity metrics used by clustering algorithms are typically based on distance metrics (e.g., the Euclidean distance), which can be easily computed over numerical attributes. The datasets that require anonymization however usually include also categorical attributes. We therefore map the values in the domain of categorical attributes into numerical values (e.g., in our experiments we simply map the n categorical values into integer numbers in the range $[1, n]$). Third, similarly to classification, the partitions of tuples computed by the clustering algorithm must satisfy both the k -anonymity and ℓ -diversity requirements. To satisfy k -anonymity, each cluster must include at least k tuples. For this reason, we use clustering algorithms that guarantee that each generated cluster includes a minimum number of tuples (constrained K-means in our experiments, see Section VI). To satisfy ℓ -diversity, each cluster must include at least ℓ well-represented values for the sensitive attribute. To this purpose, we perform a post-processing that merges clusters that do not satisfy ℓ -diversity. In particular, each cluster that has less than

FIGURE 5. An example of clustering obtained from the relation in Fig. 2(a) before (a), and after (b) the post-processing.

ℓ different values for the sensitive attribute is merged with the cluster “most similar” to it (see Appendix B). (Intuitively, this is in line with the principle at the basis of clustering, which keeps together similar tuples.) If there are more clusters having the same similarity (e.g., distance between centroids in our implementation) to the cluster that does not satisfy ℓ -diversity, we select the one with the highest number of different values for the sensitive attribute. The rationale is that this choice could limit the number of merge operations necessary to guarantee ℓ -diversity for the computed clustering (if one of the clusters already satisfies ℓ -diversity, no further merge is needed). We stop the post-processing when the resulting clustering is (k, ℓ) -compliant, as formally defined in the following.

Definition IV.2 ((k, ℓ)-compliant clustering): Let $R(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ be a relation with s the sensitive attribute in $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$, and C be a clustering built over R . C is a (k, ℓ) -compliant clustering iff for each cluster $C \in C$, C includes at least k tuples, and C includes tuples with at least ℓ well-represented values for s .

Example IV.2 (Clustering): Fig. 5(a) illustrates an example of clustering for the relation in Fig. 2(a), where attribute Job has been projected out (since it was added for classification and hence does not apply to clustering). In the figure, we represent the tuples in the relation as points in a multi-dimensional space, with a dimension for each attribute in the quasi-identifier (i.e., Age and State). The clustering is computed assuming $k=\ell=2$ and results in four clusters: c_1 and c_2 , which contain four tuples each; and c_3 and c_4 , which contain two tuples each. The resulting clustering is not (2,2)-compliant since the two tuples in cluster c_3 (i.e., t_4 and t_{12}) have the same value (300) for sensitive attribute Income. The post-processing phase then merges c_3 with its “most similar” cluster, that is, cluster c_4 . Fig. 5(b) illustrates the clustering after the merge operation.

V. GROUP ANONYMIZATION

The goal of the second phase is to independently anonymize each group of tuples obtained in the previous phase (i.e. leaf nodes of the (k, ℓ) -compliant decision tree and clusters of the (k, ℓ) -compliant clustering, respectively). These groups include tuples that are close (or equal) in values for the quasi-identifier attributes that influence classification or

clustering ensures minimizing the impact of generalization on them. The problem becomes then to compute a generalization that produces a (k, ℓ) -anonymous version of each group of tuples while minimizing information loss. This can be achieved with classical approaches for k -anonymity and ℓ -diversity. In particular, we consider the application of Mondrian [9], a multi-dimensional algorithm that provides an efficient and effective approach for achieving k -anonymity (which we extend with ℓ -diversity). Similarly to clustering algorithms, Mondrian leverages a representation of the data as points in a multi-dimensional space, mapping each quasi-identifier attribute to a dimension, and each combination of values of the quasi-identifier attributes to a point in such space (multiple tuples with the same coordinates translate into a point with a multiplicity greater than 1). We consider values in attribute domains to be represented along axes according to the same order used in the first phase of TA_DA for clustering. Mondrian then recursively partitions the multi-dimensional space in two sub-spaces by selecting a dimension (i.e., an attribute in the quasi-identifier) and a split point (i.e., a value in the domain of such an attribute), in such a way that each sub-space includes at least k points (i.e., tuples) with at least ℓ well-represented values for the sensitive attribute. The process terminates when any further partitioning would generate sub-spaces with less than k points (or the points in the sub-spaces would have less than ℓ different values for the sensitive attribute). Finally, all the tuples in each subspace are generalized to the same combination of (generalized) values for the quasi-identifier. The anonymized version of the dataset is then obtained through the union of the anonymized groups of tuples representing the leaves of the (k, ℓ) -compliant decision tree or the clusters of the (k, ℓ) -compliant clustering. Clearly, being each group of tuples (k, ℓ) -anonymous, also their union is, as formally captured by the theorem in Appendix A.

Example V.1 (Group Anonymization): Consider the original relation in Fig. 2(a). Consider, first the case of classification. The decision tree is illustrated in Fig. 4, where again the quasi-identifier is the pair $(\text{Age}, \text{State})$. Anonymization is applied independently on the four leaves of the decision tree. For the leaf nodes with two tuples no further split can be performed. No further split can be performed also on the fourth leaf, since any split will certainly create new leaves that have all tuples with the same value for the sensitive attribute, therefore violating ℓ -diversity. For all these leaves, anonymization is achieved by generalizing sets of age values to the smallest interval including them. For the third leaf node with four tuples, also reported in Fig. 6(a) and in the multi-dimensional space in Fig. 6(b), Mondrian will perform a split over attribute Age (the only one having different values for the tuples in the group) resulting in two groups (Fig. 6(c)), on which again attribute Age is then generalized. The resulting generalized relation is the one illustrated in Fig. 2(b).

Consider now the clustering in Fig. 5(b) on the same table in Fig. 2(a), with $(\text{Age}, \text{State})$ as quasi-identifier. Anonymization is applied independently on the three clusters. Cluster

FIGURE 6. Relation table representing the third leaf of the decision tree (a) with its spatial representation and partitioning (b), and the corresponding (2,2)-anonymous version (c).

FIGURE 7. Relation tables representing clusters c_1 (a) and c_2 (b) with their spatial representation and partitioning, and the corresponding (2,2)-anonymous version.

c_3' cannot be further split (since any split would violate ℓ -diversity, as discussed above). Both cluster c_1 and cluster c_2 can instead be split over attribute State (distinguishing between MN and CS) resulting in two groups with two tuples each to be generalized reporting the age interval for each pair of tuples (see Fig. 7). Fig. 2(b) reports the table obtained generalizing the clusters in Fig. 5(b).

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We conducted a series of experiments to evaluate the effectiveness of TA_DA in enabling anonymization while maintaining utility for a downstream classification or clustering task. In the following, we first describe the methodology applied and the datasets used in the experimental evaluation (Section VI-A), and then report and discuss the experimental results for classification (Section VI-B) and clustering (Section VI-C).

A. METHODOLOGY AND DATASETS

Our experimental evaluation has the goal of comparing the performance of a data analytics task (i.e., classification or clustering) when considering anonymization of the dataset following a classical approach and when performing

TABLE 1. Overview of the attributes in the considered datasets

Dataset	QI		Label (λ)	Sensitive (s)	Others
	Categorical	Numeric			
<i>Bank</i>	job marital education housing loan	age balance duration	y (2 values)	default (2 values)	pdays previous campaign poutcome contact day_of_week month
<i>Nursery</i>	parents_has_nurs form children housing finance health		class (5 values)	social (3 values)	
<i>Cust_seg</i>	gender ever_married graduated profession	age work_exp fam_size	segment (4 values)	spending_score (3 values)	var_1

anonymization with **TA_DA** (i.e., considering the data analytics task for which data are released). As a baseline for evaluating the impact of anonymization on the data analytics task, we considered the performance of the data analytics task over the original (raw) datasets.

We therefore compared the results obtained running the downstream data analytics algorithm on three versions of each dataset: *i*) raw dataset; *ii*) dataset anonymized using a traditional anonymization approach (denoted **Anon**); *iii*) dataset anonymized using **TA_DA**. For both *ii*) and *iii*) the anonymization step was performed with Mondrian revised to support ℓ -diversity. We analyzed the results obtained varying k (considering values 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 50) and ℓ (considering values 1, 2, 3, according to the number of distinct values for the sensitive attribute in the datasets). The results reported in this section have been obtained as the average over three runs.

To simulate the presence of multiple data controllers, we randomly partitioned each original dataset in different datasets (on which we then operated independently). For simplicity, we assumed k and ℓ to be the same for all data controllers.

We performed experiments on different publicly available real-world datasets. The datasets have been first pre-processed to suppress identifiers and remove incomplete tuples. We report here the results on datasets: *Bank* and *Nursery*, from the UCI machine learning repository and *Customer_segmentation*, from the Kaggle platform. The datasets, whose attributes are reported in Table 1, are as follows.

- *Bank*¹ (45,211 tuples). It refers to direct marketing campaigns based on phone calls related to a Portuguese banking institution. It describes individuals using both numeric and categorical attributes. We consider as sensitive the binary attribute `default` that can assume two values stating whether the individual has credit in default. The label attribute for classification is `y` that represents whether a client of the bank has subscribed a bank term deposit and has two possible values: ‘yes’ and ‘no’.

- *Nursery*² (12,960 tuples). It contains information derived from a hierarchical decision model ranking nursery school applicants. It describes individuals using categorical attributes. We consider as sensitive the categorical attribute `social` that represents the social conditions of the family of the applicant and can assume three values. The label attribute for classification is `class` that represents the decisions and has five possible values: ‘not_recom’, ‘recommend’, ‘very_recom’, ‘priority’, and ‘spec_prior’.
- *Customer_segmentation*³ (13,330 tuples). It includes information on the customers of an automotive company. It describes individuals using both numeric and categorical attributes. We consider as sensitive the categorical attribute `spending_score` that represents the individual’s spending score and can assume three values. The label attribute for classification is `segment` that represents the market segment and has four possible values: ‘A’, ‘B’, ‘C’, and ‘D’.

For clustering, the label attribute (which was considered for classification) of each dataset has been discarded from consideration, since it does not apply to clustering.

B. EXPERIMENTS FOR CLASSIFICATION

For classification, the decision tree used in the first phase of our approach has been generated using the C4.5 algorithm [10], and the downstream classifier is a neural network. The categorical and numerical attributes have been transformed as follows.

- *Categorical attributes*. Each categorical attribute is replaced with x binary attributes (one for each possible value of the attribute). Data values are then encoded through their representation via the binary attributes, setting to 1 the binary attribute(s) corresponding to their value(s). Scalar values will have only one binary attribute set to 1 (single-hot encoding) while sets of values (resulting from generalization) may have more than one attribute set to 1 (multi-hot encoding). For instance, with reference to the table in Fig. 2(c), attribute `State` will be represented using three binary attributes (`StateCA`, `StateMN`, and `StateTX`), and its generalized value in tuple t_2 encoded with the first two attributes set to 1 and the latter set to 0.
- *Numerical attributes*. Scalar values of each numerical attribute a are standardized, that is, each value v is substituted with $(v - \mu_a)/\sigma_a$, where μ_a is the mean of the values in the relation for attribute a and σ_a is their standard deviation. For interval values (resulting from generalization), transformation is preceded by replacing each interval value with its mid point. For instance, with respect to the table in Fig. 2(c), Age interval [40–64] in generalized tuples t_6 , t_7 and t_{11} is replaced by 52.

¹[Online]. Available: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/222/bank+marketing>

²[Online]. Available: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/76/nursery>

³[Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/kaushikuresh147/customer-segmentation>

FIGURE 8. Accuracy and $F1_{macro}$ varying k and ℓ for the *Bank* dataset.

Each transformed anonymized datasets has then been split in a training set and a test set, and the training sets have been used to train a classifier. We built a neural network with three hidden layers with 64, 32, and 16 neurons, respectively. We used the ReLu activation function and the Adam optimizer.⁴

We evaluated the performance of the neural network (trained over the anonymized datasets and the raw datasets) by measuring the *accuracy* and the $F1_{macro}$ score. The accuracy is the ratio between the number of correct predictions and the total number of predictions. It then measures the percentage of correct classifications that a trained machine learning model achieves. The $F1_{macro}$ score is defined as the average of the class-wise F1 scores (i.e., the harmonic means of precision and recall) and is used for a multi-class classification problem. Formally, given a classification problem with a set C of classes, the $F1_{macro}$ score is defined as: $F1_{macro} = \frac{\sum_{c \in C} F1(c)}{n}$ where $F1(c)$ is the F1 score computed for class c .

Figs. 8–10 illustrate the results of our experiments, in terms of accuracy and $F1_{macro}$, varying k and ℓ and assuming three data controllers. In the figures, the orange (light gray in b/w) lines refer to the results obtained training the neural network using the dataset anonymized with TA_DA and the blue (dark gray in b/w) lines refer to the results obtained training the neural network using the dataset anonymized with Anon. For each dataset and for each value of ℓ , we draw two line charts showing accuracy and $F1_{macro}$ score, respectively. As it is visible from the figures, TA_DA performs better than (or is comparable with) Anon for all datasets and values of k and ℓ .

Accuracy. The experiments (line charts in the first column of Figs. 8–10) show that the accuracy tends to decrease as the value of k and ℓ increases. This trend is due to the fact that higher values for k and ℓ require a higher amount of generalization, thus implying higher information loss that in turn produces a decrease in the effectiveness of the anonymized datasets in the learning process.

FIGURE 9. Accuracy and $F1_{macro}$ varying k and ℓ for the *Nursery* dataset.

FIGURE 10. Accuracy and $F1_{macro}$ varying k and ℓ for the *Customer_segmentation* dataset.

⁴<https://scikit-learn.org/stable>

F1_{macro}. The F1_{macro} score has a similar trend as the accuracy across all datasets (line charts in the second column of Figs. 8–10). The experiments also show that, even though ℓ -diversity imposes stricter requirements on anonymization with respect to k -anonymity alone it has limited impact on the capability of the neural network to learn from the anonymized data. Furthermore, the F1_{macro} score of TA_DA is constantly higher than the F1_{macro} score of Anon apart from a few cases. For some configurations, the results obtained with TA_DA and Anon are so close that it is not possible to say that one is better than the other. This happens, for example, with small values of k . As k grows, the effect of grouping tuples according to the downstream classification task performed by TA_DA shows consistently better results than Anon.

C. EXPERIMENTS FOR CLUSTERING

The experimental evaluation has been performed by considering *K-means* [11] as clustering algorithm both in the first phase of TA_DA and in the downstream task. The choice of K-means is mainly due to its large use in machine learning. We specifically considered the implementation of a constrained K-means in scikit-learn, fixing the minimum number of tuples in each cluster to be the anonymity parameter k . We considered the number of clusters for the first phase of TA_DA equal to the number of tuples in the dataset divided by $2k$ ($2k$ has been proved to be the minimum number of tuples necessary for Mondrian to possibly partition a dataset [9]). The number of clusters considered for the downstream task is 5.

Since the considered clustering algorithm receives as input only numerical values and the datasets used in our experimental evaluation include both categorical and numerical attributes, categorical attributes are first transformed into numerical attributes. To this purpose, we simply map the n values in the domain of each categorical attribute onto integer values in the range $[1, n]$, and then standardize. All the (numerical) attributes in the datasets are standardized as well before running TA_DA, adopting a similar approach described in the previous subsection for neural networks.

We evaluated the performance of the downstream classifier (running over the anonymized datasets and the raw datasets) by measuring the *Adjusted Rand Index* (ARI [12], [13]) and the *Normalized Mutual Information* (NMI [14]) metrics, and considering the clustering computed over raw data as the baseline. Intuitively, ARI provides a measure of the similarity between two clustering results based on a pairwise comparison of how tuples are organized in clusters (i.e., assume in two clusterings the same decision is made to assign a given pair of tuples in the same cluster or to separate the pair in two different clusters, the agreement between the two clusterings is measured by an ARI increase). Similarly to ARI, also NMI compares clusterings, but it differs in the approach, which is based on Information Theory. Moreover, NMI is normalized, not adjusted. We opted for ARI and NMI over metrics measuring the cohesiveness or separation of clusters (e.g., the Silhouette Coefficient [15]) because we aim at comparing the output of clustering obtained over raw data versus

FIGURE 11. ARI and NMI varying k and ℓ for the *Bank* dataset.

FIGURE 12. ARI and NMI varying k and ℓ for the *Nursery* dataset.

anonymized data to assess the impact of anonymization on clustering, rather than the quality of the computed clustering per se.

Figs. 11–12 show the ARI and NMI varying k and ℓ . The figures report the results for the case of three data controllers for *Nursery* and *Customer_segmentation*, and nine data controllers for *Bank*, to consider contexts with different numbers of data controllers, also based on the size of the original datasets. In the figures, the orange (light gray in b/w) lines refer to TA_DA and the blue (dark gray in b/w) lines refer to

FIGURE 13. ARI and NMI varying k and ℓ for the *Customer_segmentation* dataset.

Anon. For each dataset and for each value of ℓ , we draw two line charts showing ARI and NMI.

The figures show that NMI and ARI have a similar trend across all datasets. The values of ARI and NMI measured for TA_DA are consistently above the results obtained by Anon, demonstrating the advantages of a target-aware approach.

VII. DISCUSSION

The design of TA_DA has been driven by the main objective of anonymizing data while taking into consideration the downstream data analytics task. There are some design aspects that would deserve a further investigation and experimental evaluation, as discussed in the following.

Categorical attributes. As discussed in Section IV, most distance metrics used by clustering algorithms operate on numerical attributes only. We therefore mapped categorical attributes into numerical attributes. Since our focus in this paper is not the quality of clustering per se, but rather to measure the results obtained over data anonymized using TA_DA and a classical anonymization algorithm (w.r.t. the clustering obtained over raw data) no major emphasis has been devoted to the investigation of approaches for managing categorical attributes. We note however that categorical attributes could be mapped into numerical values using other approaches. For instance, the mapping could be based on a single-hot-encoding strategy (i.e., defining a binary attribute for each value in the categorical attribute domain and setting

to 1 the binary attribute corresponding to the value assumed by the categorical attribute in the considered tuple), similarly to what discussed for neural networks. The mapping could also be based on the definition of a generalization hierarchy on the domain of the categorical attribute, which is then translated into numerical values ordered according to the leaves in the hierarchy and at a distance that reflects the semantics of the attribute values (and their similarity).

ℓ -diversity. To generate a (k, ℓ) -compliant clustering (see Section IV), we merged each cluster generated by K-means that does not satisfy ℓ -diversity with the closest (measured as the distance between centroids) cluster. While this approach demonstrated to provide good results (see Section VI), there could be alternative approaches to guarantee ℓ -diversity. As an example, the distance between clusters can be measured in different ways (e.g., the maximum/minimum distance between pairs of tuples in the two clusters). Also, instead of using a distance-based metric, the merge of clusters could be driven by a metric based on information loss, aiming at reducing the number of merge operations and/or the amount of generalization needed to guarantee ℓ -diversity. We note that ℓ -diversity could be guaranteed also using a completely different approach, for example, by swapping tuples between clusters to guarantee that both clusters satisfy ℓ -diversity. Similarly, a tuple could be moved from a cluster satisfying ℓ -diversity to another cluster that does not satisfy ℓ -diversity, in such a way that after the update both clusters satisfy ℓ -diversity. Moving single tuples may have the advantage of maintaining the number of clusters generated by the clustering algorithm, while merging clusters may have the advantage of providing the anonymization algorithm with more flexibility when operating on the tuples of the merged (and hence larger) clusters.

Parameter setting. In the adoption of target-aware anonymization, it is important to tailor design choice and parameters to the considered dataset and task, in terms of data distribution, semantics, and task goals. Indeed, the quality of the anonymized dataset computed by TA_DA highly depends on design choices and parameter settings. Target-aware anonymization depends on different aspects, including: the classification or clustering algorithm used in the first phase of TA_DA; the attributes considered in the first phase of TA_DA; the anonymization algorithm used in the second phase of TA_DA; the downstream data analytics task; the management of categorical attributes; the enforcement of (k, ℓ) -compliance in classification/clustering. Concluding, we cannot assume there can be a one-size fits all approach, but rather it is necessary to carefully take into account the peculiarities of the specific scenario and set TA_DA to better suit the specific needs.

VIII. RELATED WORK

The problem of studying the effects of anonymization (e.g., k -anonymity, ℓ -diversity) on machine learning models has been the subject of several works (e.g., [16], [17], [18], [19],

[20], [21], [22]). Some proposals (e.g., [20], [21], [22]) evaluate the impact of anonymization algorithms on the result of machine learning models or whether data anonymization can be sufficient as a privacy guarantee in machine learning. Other proposals (e.g., [16], [17], [18], [19]) consider a problem similar to ours, and define an anonymization strategy that takes into account the utility for the specific use for which the data are released.

The work in [19] has introduced the problem of anonymizing data depending on a workload, which can be a classification or regression model or selection/projection predicates. The work proposes a variation of Mondrian where data are split in a way that minimizes the weighted entropy over the set of resulting partitions without violating k -anonymity. The main differences with our approach are that we consider a scenario with multiple data controllers, we can anonymize data using any anonymization algorithm, and we consider also clustering as a possible downstream task. The work in [17] defines a method for learning how to generalize unseen data for classification analysis. It starts from an existing machine learning model and learns how unseen data should be generalized by training a generalizer model (i.e., a decision tree) with data labeled with the existing model's predictions. The decision tree is then used to derive a set of generalization ranges obtained by combining the split values of each attribute from the tree's internal nodes of the tree. While sharing with our work the idea of using a decision tree to build groups of "similar tuples", the problem addressed is therefore different. Also the work in [18] builds a decision tree to determine the attributes that most influence the value of the target attribute. Leaf nodes of the decision tree with more than k data items are then anonymized by suppressing all attributes that are not used along the path from the root to the considered leaf node. Otherwise, a prune procedure is applied to obtain new leaf nodes of size at least k . The anonymization via suppression is then applied on these new leaf nodes. This proposal differs from our proposal in several aspects. The decision tree is built in a different way, ℓ -diversity is not considered, and the anonymization is enforced only through suppression (in contrast to generalization), thus potentially reducing the information available for the classification task. The work in [16] proposes an approach for anonymizing data guided by relaxed functional dependencies. Such dependencies specify which subsets of attributes can be generalized and at which level, so to achieve k -anonymity while preserving data utility as much as possible. Data utility is measured in terms of classification accuracy and information gain.

Some proposals use clustering with the goal of improving the utility of anonymized datasets with respect to classical anonymization approaches (e.g., [23], [24], [25], [26], [27]). Differently from TA_DA, these solutions do not consider downstream analytics tasks, and use only attributes in the quasi-identifier for clustering tuples to the aim of minimizing generalization (and hence information loss).

IX. CONCLUSION

We addressed the problem of anonymizing data in a scenario where multiple data controllers contribute to a data analytics task. We proposed TA_DA, a data anonymization approach aware of, and driven by, the task downstream. TA_DA enables data controllers contributing with their data to a classification or clustering task to anonymize their data while maintaining utility for the downstream task. The experimental results confirm the ability of TA_DA to limit, with respect to classical anonymization approaches, the information loss caused by data anonymization and hence its effect on the performance of the downstream task. The paper leaves space for future work, including: the consideration of other privacy definitions (e.g., extend (k, ℓ) -compliance to t -closeness, use differential privacy instead of k -anonymity), the consideration of other data analytics tasks (e.g., regression), the analysis of scenarios characterized by datasets with extremely unbalanced distribution of classes and/or number of tuples, and the study of different solutions for managing categorical attributes.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Bhattacharjee, A. Islam, J. Vaidya, and A. Dasgupta, "PRIVEE: A visual analytic workflow for proactive privacy risk inspection of open data," in *Proc. IEEE Symp. Vis. Cyber Secur.*, Oklahoma City, OK, USA, Oct. 2022, pp. 1–11.
- [2] V. Ciriani, S. De Capitani di Vimercati, S. Foresti, and P. Samarati, "K-anonymous data mining: A survey," in *Privacy-Preserving Data Mining: Models and Algorithms*, C. Aggarwal and P. Yu, Eds. Berlin, Germany: Springer-Verlag, 2008.
- [3] S. De Capitani di Vimercati, S. Foresti, V. Ghirimoldi, and P. Samarati, "DT-Anon: Decision tree target-driven anonymization," in *Proc. DB-Sec*, San Jose, CA, USA, Jul. 2024, pp. 111–130.
- [4] P. Samarati, "Protecting respondents identities in microdata release," *IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng.*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 1010–1027, Nov./Dec. 2001.
- [5] A. Machanavajjhala, D. Kifer, J. Gehrke, and M. Venkitasubramaniam, " ℓ -diversity: Privacy beyond k -anonymity," *ACM Trans. Knowl. Discov. From Data*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 3–es, Mar. 2007.
- [6] S. De Capitani di Vimercati, S. Foresti, G. Livraga, and P. Samarati, "Data privacy: Definitions and techniques," *Int. J. Uncertainty, Fuzziness Knowl.-Based Syst.*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 793–817, Dec. 2012.
- [7] J. Han, M. Kamber, and J. Pei, *Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques*. Burlington, MA, USA: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, 2006.
- [8] X. Ran, Y. Xi, Y. Lu, X. Wang, and Z. Lu, "Comprehensive survey on hierarchical clustering algorithms and the recent developments," *Artif. Intell. Rev.*, vol. 56, no. 8, pp. 8219–8264, Aug. 2023.
- [9] K. LeFevre, D. J. DeWitt, and R. Ramakrishnan, "Mondrian multi-dimensional k -anonymity," in *Proc. IEEE 22nd Int. Conf. Data Eng. Workshops*, Atlanta, GE, USA, Apr. 2006, Art. no. 25.
- [10] J. R. Quinlan, *C4.5: Programs for Machine Learning*. San Francisco, CA, USA: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., 1993.
- [11] J. MacQueen, "Some methods for classification and analysis of multivariate observations," in *Proc. 5th Berkeley Symp. Math. Statist. Probability*, Berkeley, CA, USA, 1967, pp. 281–297.
- [12] W. M. Rand, "Objective criteria for the evaluation of clustering methods," *J. Amer. Stat. Assoc.*, vol. 66, no. 336, pp. 846–50, Dec. 1971.
- [13] L. Hubert and P. Arabie, "Comparing partitions," *J. Classification*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 193–218, Dec. 1985.
- [14] N. X. Vinh, J. Epps, and J. Bailey, "Information theoretic measures for clusterings comparison: Variants, properties, normalization and correction for chance," *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 11, no. 95, pp. 2837–2854, 2010.
- [15] P. J. Rousseeuw, "Silhouettes: A graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis," *J. Comput. Appl. Math.*, vol. 20, pp. 53–65, Nov. 1987.

- [16] L. Caruccio, D. Desiato, G. Polese, G. Tortora, and N. Zannone, “A decision-support framework for data anonymization with application to machine learning processes,” *Inf. Sci.*, vol. 613, pp. 1–32, Oct. 2022.
- [17] A. Goldsteen, G. Ezov, R. Shmelkin, M. Moffie, and A. Farkas, “Data minimization for GDPR compliance in machine learning models,” *AI Ethics*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 477–491, Aug. 2022.
- [18] S. Kisilevich, L. Rokach, Y. Elovici, and B. Shapira, “Efficient multi-dimensional suppression for k -anonymity,” *IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng.*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 334–347, Mar. 2010.
- [19] K. LeFevre, D. DeWitt, and R. Ramakrishnan, “Workload-aware anonymization,” in *Proc. 12th ACM SIGKDD Int. Conf. Knowl. Discov. Data Mining*, Philadelphia, PA, USA, Aug. 2006, pp. 277–286.
- [20] K. Mancuhan and C. Clifton, “Instance-based learning with ℓ -diversity,” *Trans. Data Privacy*, vol. 10, pp. 203–235, Dec. 2017.
- [21] N. Senavirathne and V. Torra, “On the role of data anonymization in machine learning privacy,” in *Proc. IEEE 19th Int. Conf. Trust, Secur. Privacy Comput. Commun.*, Guangzhou, China, Dec. 2020, pp. 664–675.
- [22] D. Slijepčević, M. Henz, L.D.I Klausner, T. Dam, P. Kieseberg, and M. Zeppelzauer, “ k -anonymity in practice: How generalisation and suppression affect machine learning classifiers,” *Comput. Secur.*, vol. 111, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 102488.
- [23] G. Aggarwal et al., “Achieving anonymity via clustering,” *ACM Trans. Algorithms*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1–19, Jun. 2010.
- [24] X. He, H. Chen, Y. Chen, Y. Dong, P. Wang, and Z. Huang, “Clustering-based k -anonymity,” in *Proc. PAKDD*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, May/June 2012, pp. 405–417.
- [25] G. Loukides and J.-H. Shao, “An efficient clustering algorithm for k -anonymisation,” *J. Comput. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 188–202, Mar. 2008.
- [26] M. Nergiz and C. Clifton, “Thoughts on k -anonymization,” *Data Knowl. Eng.*, vol. 63, no. 3, pp. 622–645, Dec. 2007.
- [27] Y. Yan, E. Herman, A. Mahmood, T. Feng, and P. Xie, “A weighted k -member clustering algorithm for k -anonymization,” *Computing*, vol. 103, no. 10, pp. 2251–2273, Oct. 2021.

SABRINA DE CAPITANI DI VIMERCATI (Senior Member, IEEE) is a professor at the Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy. Her research interests are in data security and privacy. She has published 240 papers in journals, conference proceedings, and books. She has been a visiting researcher at SRI International, CA, USA, and George Mason University, VA, USA.
<https://decapitani.di.unimi.it>

SARA FORESTI (Senior Member, IEEE) is a professor at the Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy. Her research interests are in data security and privacy. She has published more than 120 papers in journals, conference proceedings, and books. She has been a visiting researcher at George Mason University, VA, USA. She chairs the IFIP WG 11.3 on Data and Applications Security and Privacy.
<https://foresti.di.unimi.it>

VALERIO GHIRIMOLDI is a cybersecurity consultant. He has a master’s degree in computer science. His research interests include machine learning, data security and privacy, and networks.

PIERANGELA SAMARATI (Fellow, IEEE) is a professor at the Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy. Her main research interests are in data protection, security, and privacy. She has published more than 300 papers in journals, conference proceedings, and books. She has been a visiting researcher at Stanford University, CA, USA, SRI International, CA, USA, and George Mason University, VA, USA. She is a Fellow of ACM, IEEE, and IFIP.
<https://samarati.di.unimi.it>

SERGIO BAREZZANI (Senior Member, IEEE) has more than 25 years of IT experience (private/public sectors) covering roles such as CIO, VP, leading digital transformation programs in international contexts, and is currently engaged in the NRRP research initiative “Security and Rights in Cyberspace”. He has earned a master’s degree in electronic engineering, master in data protection (Politecnico di Milano), master in business administration (SDA Bocconi).